

Additional material for the paper ‘Measuring accessibility through surprisal: a cross-linguistic study of personal pronouns’ – Appendix D: Monolingual Models

1. Correlation of Surprisal from mGPT and monolingual models

In order to evaluate whether surprisal from a multilingual language model like mGPT (Shliazko et al. 2022) can be used in a typological study like ours, we compare surprisal from this model to surprisal to of a series of monolingual language models trained on the Greek, Italian, Turkish and Ukrainian section of the Wiki-40b dataset (Guo et al. 2020). We then correlate surprisal of these monolingual models with surprisal from mGPT for all pronoun positions in miniciep+ (Figure 1) and for the category combinations which we employ in our regression models (Figure 2).

We train the smallest version of the OPT architecture (Zhang et al. 2022) on the full train set of the Greek, Italian, Turkish and Ukrainian section of Wiki-40b for 3 epochs, with a BPE vocabulary of 30000 items derived from the corresponding section of miniCIEP+. During training, we use lossy context (Kuribayashi et al 2022) to force the model to condition on shorter context down to the empty context.

Figure 1: Monolingual lossy-context surprisal on Wiki-40b vs. mGPT surprisal for individual pronoun positions.

Figure 2: Monolingual lossy-context surprisal on Wiki-40b vs. mGPT surprisal for category groupings in our regression models.

We find positive correlations on the level of the individual pronoun, though the strength of the correlation is only middling, and weak in the case of Ukrainian. As we shift to surprisal averaged over multiple groupings of categories (Figure 2), the correlations for Greek, Italian and Turkish become more pronounced, but now no correlation is found for Ukrainian. We attribute this to the relatively high number of pronoun types in Ukrainian (three genders, two numbers and 6 cases), indicating that the training corpus for this language may need to be larger.

We take the positive medium to strong correlations to indicate that the results of our statistical analysis would not change dramatically.

2. Surprisal curves for synrole and person

Figure 3: Average surprisal of 1st, 2nd and 3rd person pronouns over multiple context sizes.

Figure 4: Average surprisal subject and object (non-subject) pronouns over multiple context sizes.

We observe an overfitting effect for Ukrainian for 3rd person pronouns (the most morphologically diverse class). This reinforces the point made in 1., namely that more than the 200 million tokens in the Wiki-40b corpus are needed to train a model than can generalize to very long context sizes (>> 31 tokens).

References

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